

NEW AND MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN

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ABSTRACT

The methodology of the Russian language as a pedagogical science is less than two hundred years old. It has its own object-subject area, its content, a system of fundamental concepts, research methods, which differs from other sciences. Currently, there are three branches of the methodology of the Russian language: the methodology of the Russian language as a mother tongue, the methodology of the Russian language in a non-Russian school

Such outstanding scientists as F.I. Buslaev, K. D. Ushinsky, I.I. Sreznevsky, V.P. Sheremetevsky, D.I. Tikhomirov, F.F. Fortunatov, A.D. Alferov and others. In the fundamental work of F.I. Buslaev "On Teaching the Russian Language", published in 1844, for the first time laid the foundations of the theory of teaching the Russian language. The author considered the main task of teaching students the Russian language to be the development of their "innate gift of speech" through the analysis of samples of fiction and folklore. Reading, writing, speech development, work on grammar and vocabulary, etymology of F.I. Buslaev recommended to consider in aggregate [1-3].

The concept of modern education has determined the goal of the teacher's professional activity - to form students' ability to successfully socialize in society, actively adapt to the labor market. The consequence of this is the development of innovative technologies in teaching. Innovative methods are characterized by a new style of organizing educational and cognitive activities of

students. Modern teachers recognize that the technology of problem-based learning presents the maximum opportunities in the development of creative abilities and intellectual activity [4-6].

In general, we can talk about two groups of strategies: directly affecting learning and promoting learning.

The former may include:

- cognitive strategies that students use to make sense of the material,
- memorization strategies - for storing it in memory,
- compensatory strategies - help to cope with difficulties arising in the process of communication.

In recent decades, in connection with the development of modern educational technologies, audio and video recordings, computer programs, and distance learning have been widely introduced into the educational process. Information technologies enrich the educational process in many areas of knowledge, in a wide variety of learning environments and at all levels. This fully

applies to teaching foreign languages, especially abroad, where direct contact with the target language is limited. Within the framework of this technology, the student really becomes an active subject of the educational process, independently owning knowledge and solving cognitive tasks. The purpose of such techniques is to activate, optimize, and intensify the process of cognition. Innovative teaching involves the mandatory inclusion of students in activities, collective forms of work, exchange of views.

The features of innovative teaching are:

- work ahead of the curve, anticipation of development;
- openness to the future;
- focus on personality, its development;
- the obligatory presence of elements of creativity;
- partner type of relationship: cooperation, co-creation, mutual assistance, etc.

Innovations in education are called innovations, innovations in the content of education, in the forms and methods of teaching, in the relationship "teacher - student", the use of information technologies for teaching, the introduction of new equipment in the organization of the educational process, its management

Innovative technologies make it possible to realize one of the main goals of teaching the Russian language and literature - to provide an opportunity to move from studying a subject as a system-structural education to studying it as a means of communication and thinking, and transfer educational and cognitive activities to a productive and creative level.

In the modern ("information") society, one of the rapidly developing methods and arousing great interest from students is the use of Internet resources as an innovative approach to teaching.

The idea of using the Internet in education is not new. Since the early 1990s, national and international computer networks have been widely used for educational purposes within the framework of various educational approaches. Both students and teachers were able to exchange information in a mode that does not depend on time and place. New digital technologies have freed the human mind for more creative tasks that contribute to personal development. This allows students to interact creatively with both classmates and the teacher.

The Internet can be viewed as a "means of production", including in the educational process. It is used both as an inexhaustible source of information and as a new communicative environment in which educational work can be organized in a new way.

It contributes to the formation of a scientific style of speech, self-assessment of their own statements, it turns out to be an effective form of control and self-control, children learn to work independently, to use scientific literature. The theory serves as the basis for the content of the workshop. The leading goal is the formation of theoretical thinking, which will allow students to independently select, study information and apply the knowledge gained in practice.

In accordance with the tasks of repeating the sections, seminars can be organized on the following topics: "Word composition and word formation", "Morphology. Independent and service parts of speech", "Punctuation of a simple sentence", etc.

Lessons of this kind require careful preparation by both the student and the teacher. The educational and educational value of the seminars is undeniable. It consists, first of all, in the fact that schoolchildren learn to work independently with scientific literature, to build their performances in accordance with the proposed plan, and this prepares students for studying at a university.

One of the modern requirements for a Russian lesson is working with text. In this regard, I use in my work such a lesson form as research. The very name "lesson - research" shows the main task - the study of language material on the basis of texts.

When preparing for such a lesson, special attention should be paid to the choice of text. The text should be highly artistic, while it is necessary to take into account both the age characteristics of the students and the volume of the studied material. It is advisable to use for the analysis the texts of different authors, united by a common theme, texts of different styles and types of speech, in order to subsequently carry out a comparative and contrastive analysis.

The Internet allows you to implement various techniques, provide methodological developments, diversify the educational process, make it more attractive, take into account the needs and interests of the subject of training, the level of his training, promptly and purposefully control the work of students, effectively manage it

I also find it effective in some lessons to read with stops and Bloom's questions (a conventional name for a methodological technique for organizing reading using different types of questions).

The development of critical thinking is also facilitated by unconventional lessons that increase the student's interest both in the subject and in learning in general. I see creativity in such lessons not in entertainment, but in the selection of such tasks, such didactic material, which with its novelty, unusual presentation (travel, meeting, competition, game, etc.), causing surprise, activates the student's attention and thinking. Getting into an unusual situation, the child is involved in activities, cooperation with the teacher, thus creating a positive emotional background, the intellectual and volitional spheres begin to function actively, knowledge is more easily assimilated, skills and abilities are formed faster.

This is facilitated by the creation of conditions in non-standard lessons for mobilizing the creative reserves of both the teacher and the student. Preparation for non-traditional lessons is carried out very carefully, and this, as a rule, requires a lot of effort and time from both the teacher and the student. In my practice, I most successfully use several non-traditional forms of the lesson: workshop, quiz, research, travel, dialogue based on a problem situation, business game, test. The choice depends on several conditions: firstly, I take into account the age characteristics of students, and secondly, the tasks, goals, content of training in connection with the topic under study

An innovative approach to teaching allows you to organize the educational process in such a way that the lesson is both fun and beneficial for the child, without turning into just fun or a game. And, perhaps, precisely in such a lesson, as Cicero said, "the eyes of the hearer will light up against the eyes of the speaker."

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